

Exploring Size and Shape with Multivariate Ratio Analysis (MRA)

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These guidelines follow from a paper on the analysis of ratios in multivariate morphometry (Baur and Leuenberger 2011). Recall that the principal aim of a morphometric study is the analysis of variation in size, shape and allometry (i.e., size related shape variation, see e.g., Gould 1966, Pimentel 1979). Based on this claim, we developed several tools adapted to principal component analysis (PCA) and linear discriminant analysis (LDA) that allow the user to analyse each of these issues separately. In contrast to earlier multivariate methods for the analysis of size and shape (e.g., Jolicoeur 1963), the numerical results obtained by our methods can be directly used for diagnoses, descriptions and identification keys in the form of ratios and are thus addressed to the needs of practicing taxonomists.

A user's perspective is adopted here. The methods are demonstrated with a dataset of the *Dibrachys cavus* complex (Hymenoptera: Pteromalidae), see Material and Methods section in Peters and Baur (2011) for a complete description. The datafile can be accessed [here](#). All analyses were generated with the statistical software R (R Core Team 2020). R-scripts for reproducing Figs. 2-9 may be obtained together with this paper (citation below), the required MRA source files from [here](#).

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Size and Shape: a Matter of Definition

Before I start demonstrating the new methods, it is necessary to understand the particular framework of size and shape used here. This is best illustrated with a simple, two-dimensional object, such as a sheet of paper. To begin with, let's have a look at an A4 paper with a length of 298 mm and a breadth of 210 mm. Its sides form a ratio of 1.42. In contrast, an A5 paper has a length of 210 mm and a breadth of 148 mm. The sides have exactly the same proportions, however, as they also form a ratio of 1.42. Hence, the two paper formats have the same shape but obviously differ in size. More specifically they differ along the so called isometric size axis that is defined here as the geometric mean of length and breadth. For an A4 paper isometric size is about 250.2 mm and for A5 it is about 176.3 mm. Now, let's have a look at an US letter paper with a length of 279 mm and a breadth of 216 mm, that is, with proportions of 1.29 and an isometric size of about 245.5 mm. An US letter therefore differs from both, the A4 and A5 paper, in size and in shape. One could say, it's format is slightly more transverse and its size is intermediate, though almost that of an A4 paper.

By looking in this manner at the size and shape of a sheet of paper, we have just applied a *specific definition* of size and shape. Mosimann (1970) was the first to formalize size and shape in a mathematical framework of ratios and also generalized it for objects with more than just two dimensions, such as the body of an insect where we can measure numerous traits. The mathematical theory developed by Mosimann is complicated, hence we are taking in trust that isometric size as defined above is simply a suitable size measure in the case of ratios.¹ Because this framework of size and shape involves isometric size, I will call for our purposes the space, it defines, the "isospace" (corresponding to size and shape as embraced by the Gould-Mosimann school of Klingenberg 1998).

¹The geometric mean has been chosen in our paper, because it gives equal weight to all variables and has favorable statistical properties (Jolicoeur 1963, Mosimann 1970). In principal, other size measures, such as area, diagonal, length or breadth of a paper would be permissible, too. Note, however, that if we take just length as size, then the A4 paper is larger than the US letter; if we take breadth, then the reverse is true. Apparently, the sides of a paper are themselves not suited as a *general* size measure. One should keep this in mind, each time a single dimension of an insect body, such as thorax breadth or body length, is used as an indication of size.

Of course, other mathematical frameworks for the definition of size and shape are possible. A frequently used framework in multivariate morphometry is given by calculating a standard PCA on the covariance matrix of the log-transformed data. Here, the first principal component represents size (e.g., Jolicoeur and Mosimann 1960, Pimentel 1979, Klingenberg 1996, Claude 2008, Baur and Leuenberger 2011). However, it does not account for isometric but for allometric size variation, hence it is considered as an allometric size axis (Jolicoeur 1963). The second and following components of such a standard PCA then define the shape space, more specifically they represent *allometry free* shape variables (in contrast, from ratios we get *isometry free* shape variables). This framework of size and shape therefore differs from isospace. Because it is related to allometric size, I refer to this space as the “allospace” (corresponding to size and shape as embraced by the Huxley-Jolicoeur school of Klingenberg 1998).

Why are these frameworks for the analysis of size and shape so important? By calculating ratios or doing a PCA of a given sample, are we not always looking at the same individuals? This is indeed so, but the crux is, that, geometrically, shape as defined in isospace differs from shape as defined in allospace. For instance, an A4 and an A5 paper, though evidently having exactly the same length to breadth ratio and only being of different size, each will have a different shape value in a standard PCA of the above three papers, simply because ratios are calculated in isospace and the PCA is performed in allospace; or, to take an example from taxonomy, a researcher might wonder that two specimens with almost identical body proportions will appear as widely separated points in a scatterplot of the second against third component of a standard PCA, only because one specimen is larger than the other (such a case is demonstrated in Figure 6 of Baur and Leuenberger 2011); or, in the worst case, two taxonomists, performing a PCA on the very same dataset, arrive at opposing conclusions, as the one working in isospace recognizes two species, while the one exploring the data in allospace can only see a single cluster of points. This may happen when one species is larger than the other and thus isometric size is very different from allometric size, which, in turn, strongly affects the shape values (Figure 1). Obviously, if one is not aware of the consequences of the different definitions of size and shape then one is at risk to interpret spurious results. Clearly, this would be a disconcerting state of affairs. One solution to the problem is to carry

out all statistical analyses in one and the same framework of size and shape. In our paper we have therefore adapted multivariate statistical methods, such as PCA and LDA, to the isospace, so that the results are equivalent to those obtained from calculating ratios. The application of our methods, in particular the PCA in isospace, PCA ratio spectrum, allometry ratio spectrum, and LDA ratio extractor, is now demonstrated in the following sections.

Figure 1: *Podagrion pachymerum* reared from a small host (red triangles) and *P. bouceki* reared from a large host (blue dots) (Hymenoptera: Torymidae): scatterplot of first versus second shape PC in isospace (left) and in allospace (right), respectively, by using the same dataset. Evidently, the framework of size and shape matters, as the two clusters in the left graph are completely intermingled in the right graph (unpublished data from Gérard Delvare, CIRAD, Montpellier).

Size and Shape Analysis in Isospace

Interpretation of principal components

Interpretation of results of a shape PCA in isospace² is first demonstrated for *Dibrachys lignicola* Graham, 1969 and *D. microgastris* (Bouché, 1834). Figure 2 shows a scatterplot of the first two principal components (PC) in shape space. From the plot it is evident that the two species are separated by the first PC. The second PC does not contribute to the separation of the

Figure 2: *Dibrachys lignicola* (black rectangles) and *D. microgastris* (red stars): scatterplot of first versus second shape PC in isospace.

²Calculation of a shape PCA in isospace involves the following steps: (1) Standardizing the data. This is achieved by log-transforming (conventionally natural logarithms are used) and centering the data, so that all variables have a mean of zero. (2) Specifying the isometric size axis. As mentioned in the introduction, isometric size is defined as the geometric mean of the raw values. This is equivalent to the arithmetic mean of the standardized log-transformed data. (3) Orthogonal projection of the standardized data matrix to the isometric size axis (geometrically, a projection at right angle). This cannot easily be explained in words (but see Baur and Leuenberger 2011, p. 815–816). However, the only important thing to note, is, that we thus get a new data matrix \mathbf{Y} of shape values. (4) Finally, a PCA is calculated on the covariance matrix of \mathbf{Y} .

species. The plot also reveals that *D. microgastri* is much more variable in shape than *D. lignicola*, in direction of the first as well as of the second PC.

Of course, it might be interesting to see how the two principal components can be interpreted and we might ask, what are the important body proportions that explain the variance of the two components? The appropriate method is the so called “PCA ratio spectrum”, a tool that allows us to interpret principal components in terms of ratios. In Figure 3 the PCA ratio spectrum for the first shape component is displayed. It is used by calculating ratios with the variables indicated by horizontal bars on the spectrum. Now, ratios calculated from two variables lying far apart, like *stigmal.vein* and *gaster.length* – here also representing the extremal points on the spectrum – contribute substantially to this component while a ratio calculated from two variables lying close to each other, like *head.breadth* and *pedicel.length*, contribute very little. Beside the ratio

Figure 3: *Dibrachys lignicola* and *D. microgastri*: PCA ratio spectrum for first shape PC in isospace.

stigma.vein:gaster.length also other ratios such as *stigma.vein:malar.space*, *stigma.vein:marginal.vein* or *eye.b:gaster.length*, *eye.breadth:malar.space* and *eye.breadth:marginal.vein* have to be considered. It is also obvious that ratios like for instance *pol:lower.face* or *pol:scutellum.breadth* explain already much less of the variation of the first shape PC. Note, that the ratio spectrum depicts an exact linear relationship of the explanatory power of each ratio; for instance, by adding the ratios *stigma.vein:pol* and *pol:gaster.length* the same amount of variation is explained as with *stigma.vein:gaster.length*.

For the second shape PC, the PCA ratio spectrum (Fig. 4) can be used in exactly the same way. Here, the confidence intervals (the blue bars) are much wider than in the spectrum of the first shape PC (especially for the variable *lower.face*). While for the first ratio spectrum the confidence intervals are in order, they are far too wide for the second ratio spectrum, meaning that the second shape PC and its ratio spectrum are actually unstable. Instability may

Figure 4: *Dibrachys lignicola* and *D. microgastri*: PCA ratio spectrum for second shape PC in isospace.

occur when the component is not significantly separated from the remaining components and may have profound effects on the results: add or remove a few specimens and the variables could be considerably shuffled on a ratio spectrum with large confidence intervals. Therefore, one shouldn't draw any far reaching conclusions from such a graph and only the PCA ratio spectrum of the first shape PC is really worth considering in the case of the two *Dibrachys* species. As we have seen above (Fig. 2), the second shape PC does not contribute anything to their differentiation, hence there is maybe also no urgent need for its interpretation.

Assessing Allometry

To assess the amount of allometry in the data, the shape PCs can be plotted against the isometric size axis Fig. 5. If the shape values are correlated with the isometric size axis then this is a sign of allometry. Judging from these plots, the first shape PC is slightly correlated with isometric size (Fig. 5, left), while the second shape PC is almost uncorrelated (Fig. 5, right). Overall, allometric variation in the data is at most very moderate.

Figure 5: *Dibrachys lignicola* (black rectangles) and *D. microgastri* (red stars): scatterplot of isometric size versus first shape PC (left) and second shape PC (right), respectively.

In case of a more significant amount of allometry it would of course be important to know the allometric behavior of the ratios that were found to explain most of the variance of the shape PC. The “allometry ratio spectrum” (Fig. 6) is the tool for finding the ratios with the strongest allometric variation. It works in a very similar manner as the PCA ratio spectrum, but this time ratios formed from distant variables are those displaying the greatest amount of allometry. In case of the two *Dibrachys* species these are ratios such as *stigma.vein:gaster.length* or *stigma.vein:marginal.vein*, while a ratio such as *pedicel.length:scape.length* shows virtually no allometric variation. One can now compare the allometry ratio spectrum with the PCA ratio spectra. For instance, the before mentioned ratios of the allometry ratio spectrum also dominate the PCA ratio spectrum of the first shape PC (Fig. 3).

Figure 6: *Dibrachys lignicola* and *D. microgastri*: allometry ratio spectrum.

Because, as stated above, the total amount of allometric variation is low, the use of any of these ratios for taxonomic purposes is uncritical. Only in the case of a very strong allometric behavior, the interpretation of ratios as reliable indicators of shape has to be questioned, as the shape differences, that we observe, might actually be due to differences in size. In practice, however, this might be rare. As an example, consider the fact that in many chalcidoids the funicular segments increase in length with body size and thus are relatively longer in larger than in smaller specimens. Sometimes the allometric behavior of this length to breadth ratio can be rather pronounced. If this ratio would be the sole tangible character for separating two otherwise very similar species, then one should carefully check whether the ratio not only reflects size differences. Several methods have been devised for this purpose. In a uni- or bivariate context, a so called “Thorpe normalization” can be applied to correct for allometry. Bartels et al. (2011) applied it to tardigrades and also explained its computation in a lucid manner. Note, that the method is mathematically equivalent to the one used by Janzon (1986) for the *Pteromalus albipennis* species group, a paper that might be better known among chalcidologists. There exists a multivariate alternative, that is, a slightly modified version of the initially mentioned PCA in allospace can be used as well. The method is described in the book of Claude (2008, p. 110–111), based on the painted turtles dataset (Jolicoeur and Mosimann 1960).

Size and Shape of Three Species of *Dibrachys*

The same plots were generated for all three species included in the revision of Peters and Baur (2011) and are compiled in Figure 7. From the upper left scatterplot it is evident that the third species, *D. verovesparum* Peters & Baur, 2011, is separated from *D. microgastri* by the first, and from *D. lignicola* by the second shape component. *D. verovesparum* is also more clearly differentiated than the other two, which reflects the fact that it was much harder to distinguish *D. microgastri* from *D. lignicola* than each of them from *D. verovesparum* (see also Peters and Baur 2011). Examination of the PCA ratio spectrum of the first shape PC discloses a rather unique composition of most important ratios, while the dominant ratio of the second shape PC, *stigmatal.vein:malar.space*, was also important in the above analysis

Figure 7: *Dibrachys lignicola* (black rectangles), *D. microgastris* (red stars), and *D. verovesparum* (green diamonds): results of size and shape analysis in isospace.

of *D. microgastris* and *D. lignicola*. Concerning allometry, the scatterplots of shape PCs versus isometric size show obviously very little correlation, hence it is of little significance that *stigma.vein:malar.space* is among the dominant ratios in the allometry ratio spectrum. In conclusion, with regard to all three species of *Dibrachys*, allometric variation is not a big issue, too.

Finding the best separation of species

By analyzing size and shape of two or more species we usually are interested in their optimal separation. Sometimes, as demonstrated here, merely with a PCA some non-overlapping groupings emerge. This must not always be the case, as a PCA does not look for the best differentiation of groups (it treats all points as belonging to a single group), but only explains the most important pattern of variation. Depending on the nature of the data, this may or may not coincide with the optimal differentiation of taxa. Therefore we might for instance ask, what are really the best characters for separating *D. microgastri* and *D. lignicola*? To address this question, a linear discriminant analysis (LDA) is usually the method of choice (Pimentel 1979, Reyment et al. 1984, Hastie et al. 2001, Claude 2008, and many more). The only problem is, that the discriminant function(s) found by a standard LDA are always a mixture of size and shape and thus incompatible for the use with body proportions. We therefore adapted the LDA to the isospace, so that the discriminant function(s) can be interpreted in terms of ratios. In particular, we developed

Figure 8: *Dibrachys lignicola* (black rectangles) and *D. microgastri* (red stars): scatterplot of the best ratios for separating the two species.

a tool called the “LDA ratio extractor” that reveals the best ratios for separation of groups. In a first step, the algorithm extracts the ratio with the highest power for discrimination. In a second step, the next best ratio is chosen that is at the same time as uncorrelated as possible with the first ratio (for a detailed description of how the algorithm works, see Methodology section in Baur and Leuenberger 2011). In Figure 8 the best and second best ratio for distinguishing *D. microgastri* from *D. lignicola* are plotted. The species are mainly separated by the best ratio, *eye.breadth:gaster.length*, that is also one of the dominant ratios in the PCA ratio spectrum of the first shape PC (as explained above, this is by coincidence). In combination with the second best ratio, *head.breadth:stigma.vein*, the two species are almost distinct, as only two specimens of *D. lignicola* fall within the range of *D. microgastri*.

Of course, one can extract the best ratios for any other groupings as well. As an example, for constructing an identification key it is often necessary to contrast a particular species with the remaining taxa under

Figure 9: *Dibrachys verovesparum* (green diamonds) and *D. lignicola* + *D. microgastri* (magenta rectangles): scatterplot of the best ratios for separating the two groups.

consideration. Hence, we might be interested to find the best ratios for separating *D. verovesparum* from the two other species. Figure 9 reveals that these are *mouth.breadth:eye.height* and *POL:eye.height*, two rather uncommon ratios that are likely to be missed by simple examination of the specimens (given a dataset with only 20 variables, already 190 informative ratios can be calculated, see formula under “Space of log-ratios” in the Methodology section of Baur and Leuenberger 2011, p. 815). The LDA ratio extractor thus always guarantees that really the best ratios are found that are at the same time least correlated.³

³Note, the method described by Peters and Baur (2011, p. 10) for finding best ratios using standard LDA is completely superseded by the LDA ratio extractor. The latter is preferable because it takes the intercorrelation of ratios into account.

Discussion

A number of body measurements are commonly collected in taxonomic research. This mainly serves two purposes. First, the raw or log-transformed variables are entered in some kind of standard multivariate statistical analysis for studying character variation and for discrimination of taxa. PCA and LDA are among the methods of choice in this respect. Second, the same measurements are integrated in descriptive works, but this time usually by calculating ratios. By doing so we should keep in mind, that, whatever the method we are using for the statistical analysis of body measurements, we are always applying a particular mathematical framework of size and shape. For instance, calculation of ratios is done in isospace, while a standard PCA is performed in allospace. As exemplified above (e.g., Figure 1), this may lead to inaccurate conclusion if one is not aware of this fact.⁴

Despite their widespread application, the use of ratios has been challenged from time to time. Recently, Bartels et al. (2011) refreshed the idea of Janzon (1986) who proposed to “correct” ratios because they do not take allometric variation into account. The technical procedure, the already mentioned Thorpe normalization going back to papers of Thorpe (1975, 1976), involves determination of the slope of the regression line of log-numerator and log-denominator of a ratio. The slope is considered as an indicator of allometry and is part of a formula for getting “allometry free” shape values (see p. 23–24 and Appendix in Bartels et al. 2011). Now, the question remains whether or not size corrected ratios should be used in descriptive works, such as identification keys or descriptions. In my view, these shape values are inappropriate in this regard for various reasons. First, Thorpe normalized shape values have to be defined with respect to a sample. Hence, as the composition of specimens in the sample changes, also the shape values of an individual change, although, matter-of-factly, the geometric proportions of the individual under consideration (e.g., a particular specimen mounted on tag) of course remain unaltered. Second, Thorpe normalized values are abstract figures, because they involve rather complicated calculations that are based on the values of other specimens. In contrast, calculation

⁴The whole issue of size and shape is a rather complicated matter that can be discussed here only briefly. For a non-mathematical, yet in-depth presentation of the subject I refer to Bookstein (1989), Klingenberg (1998) and Richtsmeier et al. (2002).

of ratios is simple and they can always be obtained from single specimens. With some experience, body proportions can often be estimated without actually taking measurements, as they reflect geometric shape in a very natural and intuitive manner. Third, the regression model used for Thorpe normalization is dependent on a sample distribution which, in turn, can be strongly influenced by deviation from normality or the presence of outliers, especially when sample size is small. Such error variance is of course not present in ratios, as they are not based on any statistical model. For these reasons, ratios seem preferable as shape values for the use in descriptive taxonomy, and Thorpe normalization should be restricted to *testing* ratios showing a strong allometric behavior (see above, last paragraph under "Assessing Allometry").

In summary, the PCA ratio spectrum, allometry ratio spectrum, and LDA ratio extractor are data mining tools that endeavor to extract the most interesting information from a morphometric dataset in terms of body ratios. Only by adapting multivariate analysis to isospace it is ensured that at any stage of the statistical analysis, size and shape of a particular specimen are fully congruent to what we see with a microscope. A taxonomist applying these methods is not only getting the power of multivariate analysis but at the same time also the shape values needed for the descriptive part of a revision. Last but not least, he is entirely freed from the pitfalls that arise by the use of different frameworks of size and shape.

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